

WAYS TO EVALUATE WRITING SKILL IN ESL CLASSES

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Abstract: The aim of this article is to find a few approaches to the evaluation of writing, there are five product variables that can be used to evaluate student writing: fluency, substance, conventions, syntax, and vocabulary. Writing samples should also be examined for a variety of writing objectives in order to provide a comprehensive picture of a student's writing performance across diverse text structures and genres. These easy classroom tools assist in identifying strengths and weaknesses, organizing education, evaluating instructional activities, providing feedback, tracking performance, and reporting progress.

Key words: text structures, fluency, substance, conventions, syntax, vocabulary, feedback, spelling, word usage.

The primary job of a teacher is to provide opportunities for writing as well as encouragement to students who try. A teacher's second role is to help students succeed in writing. The instructor accomplishes this by closely monitoring students' writing to assess strengths and weaknesses, teaching specific skills and methods based on student requirements, and providing careful feedback to reinforce newly learned skills and rectify recurring difficulties. These responsibilities demonstrate, upon closer examination, that assessment is definitely an essential component of excellent instruction. Assessment is thus a necessary component of good instruction. The first he referred to as "sizing-up" tests, which are often administered during the first week of school to provide the teacher with rapid information about the pupils before they begin instruction. The

second category, instructional assessments, is utilized for everyday duties such as lesson planning, feedback, and student progress monitoring. He referred to the third category as official assessments, which are periodic formal assessment functions such as grouping, grading, and reporting. In other words, teachers use assessments to discover strengths and weaknesses, organize instruction based on diagnosed needs, evaluate instructional activities, provide feedback, monitor performance, and report progress. Simple curriculum-based strategies for evaluating written expression can serve all of these needs. The diagnostic purposes of assessment (determining the causes of writing problems and the student's instructional requirements) are best satisfied by examining the writing process, i.e., the steps students take and the methods they employ when writing. How much planning does the student do before starting to write? Does she have a plan for arranging her ideas? What appear to be the barriers to getting thoughts down on paper? How does the pupil try to spell terms she does not recognize? Does the student reread her work? Does the student discuss or share her work with others as she writes it? What adjustments does the student make to her initial draft? To produce instructionally useful observations, the observer must first establish a conceptual model of the writing process. Educators have found little agreement on the number of phases in the writing process. The abbreviation power represents a five-step writing process: plan, organize, write, edit, and revise. Each step has its own set of substeps and tactics that evolve as students progress as writers, adapting their style to certain text structures and writing aims. The writing process can be assessed by observing students as they move through the writing processes. Having students evaluate their own writing process is also beneficial for two reasons. First, self-assessment offers students an opportunity to examine and reflect on their own approach, giving attention to critical processes that may be neglected. Second, self-assessment using a conceptual model such as POWER is a method of internalizing an explicit strategy by providing

opportunities for the learner to mentally practice the strategy stages. Similar self-assessments or observation checklists might be created for various conceptual models of the writing process.

Fluency

The first writing talent that a teacher might examine in a beginner writer is the ability to translate one's thoughts into written words. As the student's understanding of print and fine motor skills grows, he or she should become more adept at putting down words and sentences into compositions of increasing length. Very young writers' developmental path includes attempting to understand what written language is about when they read books, become aware of environmental print, and put pencil to paper. Then the youngsters try to relate their writing experiences using creative spelling. As they start to write tiny stories, they experiment with spelling patterns and learn new language patterns.

Content

The second consideration for the literary product is content. Content characteristics include composition arrangement, cohesiveness, accuracy (in expository writing), and originality (in creative writing). The classroom teacher can ask general questions on the organization of a piece, such as: Is there a decent opening sentence? Is there a definite end? Is there a logical order of subtopics or events?

Conventions

To effectively communicate, writing must be readable. Writers are expected to use normal written English rules such as correct spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and grammar, as well as readable handwriting. As a result, even if the message is conveyed, readers are more likely to reject compositions that are unappealing in form or look. Teachers have generally been more influenced by paper length, spelling, word usage, and appearance than by subject relevance or arrangement.

Vocabulary

Students' vocabulary can be evaluated based on its distinctiveness and maturity in their compositions. Vocabulary can be evaluated using either or quantitative or qualitative methods. Quantitative methods include determining the proportion of unrepeated words in the overall amount of words. A simpler classroom-based technique of looking at vocabulary is to simply take note of words that are used frequently (over-used terms) as well as new and mature words that the student employs.

Finally, continuous writing assessment is essential for effective writing instruction. Without assessment, a teacher cannot match a student's skills to appropriate tasks. A teacher cannot ensure a student's success or make required instructional adjustments unless he or she conducts frequent assessments. To conduct a complete assessment of a student's writing, the instructor must have a solid conceptual model of written expression that considers process, product, and purpose.

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